

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SCHOOL TEACHERS IN VELLORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

The present study aims to investigate emotional intelligence of school teachers working at different levels. Using random sampling technique 270 teachers from the primary, secondary and higher secondary level in different systems of education, namely, government, government aided and private schools are chosen. The Emotional Intelligence Scale Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001) have been used to assess the emotional intelligence for the present study. The data collected is subjected to statistical analysis, namely, mean, standard deviation, 't'- test, 'F'- ratio, Results show that a there is no significant difference found out between the samples of gender, location of school, type of management, level of teaching, teaching stream, teaching experience in years and marital status towards emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Keys Words: Emotional Intelligence & School Teachers

Introduction:

The word emotion has been derived from a Latin word "Emovere" which means to "stair up" or "to agitate". Thus emotion is that state of mind which deprives an individual of his equilibrium, and he feels himself disturbed and is unable to perform even ordinary activities. It is innate response and profoundly influences action for better or worse. Emotion play important role in the life of individual because they make life interesting, thrilling, exciting and beautiful. They activise our whole body. Woodworth, "emotion is moved or stirred up state of an organism; it is a stirred up state of feeling that is the way it appeared to the individual himself. Emotional intelligence refers to an ability to recognize the meanings of emotion and their relationships and to reason and problem-solve on the basis of them. Emotional intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of those emotions, and manage them. Researchers investigated dimensions of emotional intelligence by measuring related concepts, such as social skills, interpersonal competence, psychological maturity and emotional awareness, long before the term 'emotional intelligence' came into use. Teachers in schools have been teaching the rudiments of emotional intelligence since 1978, with the development of the Self Science Curriculum and the teaching of classes such as social development social and emotional learning and personal intelligence all aimed at raising the level of social and emotional competence (Goleman, 1995). Social scientists are just beginning to uncover the relationship of emotional intelligence to other phenomenon, e.g., leadership (Ashforth and Humphrey, 1995), group performance, individual performance, interpersonal/ social exchange, managing change, and conducting performance evaluations (Goleman, 1995).

Emotional intelligence represents an ability to validly reason with emotions and to use emotions to enhance thought. Emotional Intelligence encompasses the following five characteristics and abilities:

- ✓ Self-awareness--knowing your emotions, recognizing feelings as they occur, and discriminating between them
- ✓ Mood management--handling feelings so they're relevant to the current situation and you react appropriately
- ✓ Self-motivation--"gathering up" your feelings and directing yourself towards a goal, despite self- doubt, inertia, and impulsiveness
- ✓ Empathy--recognizing feelings in others and tuning into their verbal and nonverbal cues
- ✓ Managing relationships--handling interpersonal interaction, conflict resolution, and negotiations

Need for the Present Study:

Research in brain-based learning suggests that emotional health is fundamental to effective learning. According to a report from the National Center for Clinical Infant Programs, the most critical element for a student's success in school is an understanding of how to learn i.e. Emotional Intelligence. The key ingredients for this understanding are confidence, curiosity, intentionality, self-control, relatedness, capacity to communicate and ability to cooperate. These traits are all aspects of emotional intelligence. Basically, a student who learns to learn is much more apt to succeed. Emotional intelligence has proven a better predictor of future success than traditional methods like the GPA, IQ, and standardized test scores. Hence, the great interest in emotional intelligence on the part of corporations, universities, and schools nationwide. The idea of Emotional Intelligence has inspired research and curriculum development throughout these facilities. Researchers have concluded that people who manage their own feelings well and deal effectively with others are more likely to

live content lives. In addition, happy people are more apt to retain information and do so more effectively than dissatisfied people.

Building one's emotional intelligence has a lifelong impact. Many parents and educators, alarmed by increasing levels of conflict in young school children--from low self-esteem to early drug and alcohol use to depression, are rushing to teach students the skills necessary for emotional intelligence. Since emotional intelligence is a master aptitude, a capacity that profoundly affects all other abilities, either facilitating or interfering with them (Goleman, 1995), the need is felt to investigate the emotional intelligence and academic achievement among students.

Statement of the Research Problem:

The emotional intelligence of school teachers has been conducted in order to study.

Population and Sample Characteristics:

The target population for the present study is the school teachers working in different categories of schools following different systems of education at the primary, secondary and higher secondary level. From the target population a sample of 270 working teachers (48 from primary level, 97 from secondary and 125 higher secondary) are chosen.

Instrument:

The research tool used for the present study to analyze the, Emotional intelligence of different level of working teachers is Emotional Intelligence Scale Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow.

Methodology:

The sample consisted of 270 working teachers in different level were randomly selected from vellore district in Tamilnadu. In order to collect data for the study the tool which was constructed and validated by the investigator to assess the Emotional Intelligence Scale by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar (2001) has been adopted by the investigator for the present study. This tool consisted of 105 items under five alternatives such as strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which was modified and validated. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.67. This tool is also a five point scale which includes the with scoring 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively for positive items and 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 for negative items.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out significance difference between male and female school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between rural and urban school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between type of management of school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between level of teaching of school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between teaching stream of school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between teaching experiences of school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ To find out significance difference between married and unmarried school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.

Hypotheses:

There is no significance difference between following sub samples of school teachers regarding their emotional intelligence.

- ✓ Gender : Male / Female
- ✓ Location of School : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Type of Management : Government / Govt Aided / Private
- ✓ Level of Teaching : Primary / Secondary / Hr. Secondary
- ✓ Teaching Stream : Science / Maths / Arts
- ✓ Teaching Experience (Years) : Below 10/ 11 -20/ Above 21
- ✓ Marital Status : Married / Unmarried

Analysis of Data:

Gender and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 1: 't' test between Male and Female School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	140	360.22	35.17	0.783	NS
Female	130	357.00	32.15		

It is evident from the Table 1, the calculated 't' value is 0.783, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no

significant difference found out between male and female school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Location of School and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 2: 't' test between Rural and Urban School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	124	358.86	33.51	0.086	NS
Urban	146	358.50	34.03		

It is evident from the Table 2, the calculated 't' value is 0.086, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Type of Management and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 3: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Type of Management of School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	3069.634	1534.817	2	1.352	NS
Within Groups	303034.029	1134	267		
Total	306103		269		

It is evident from the Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 1.352, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Type of Management with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Level of Teaching and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 4: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Level of Teaching of School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Level of Teaching	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	3204.544	1602.272	2	1.412	NS
Within Groups	302899.119	1134.454	267		
Total	306103.663		269		

It is evident from the Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 1.412, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Level of Teaching with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Teaching Stream and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 5: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Teaching Stream of School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Teaching Stream	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	12949.088	6474.544	2	5.897	NS
Within Groups	2931154.575	1097.957	267		
Total	306103.663		269		

It is evident from the Table 5, the calculated 'F' value is 5.897, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Teaching Stream with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Teaching Experience (Year) and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 6: 'F' test among the Sub- samples of Teaching Experience (Year) of School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Teaching Experience (Year)	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	5923.495	2961.747	2	2.634	NS
Within Groups	300180.168	1124.270	267		
Total	306103.663		269		

It is evident from the Table 6, the calculated 'F' value is 2.634, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Teaching Experience (Year) with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Marital Status and Emotional Intelligence:

Table 7: 't' test between Married and Unmarried School Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Married	166	361.75	33.73	1.910	NS
Unmarried	104	353.74	33.29		

It is evident from the Table 7, the calculated 't' value is 1.910, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Married and Unmarried school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Type of Management with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Level of Teaching with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Teaching Stream with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of Teaching Experience (Year) with respect to their emotional intelligence of school teachers.
- ✓ It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between Married and Unmarried school teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Educational Implications:

- ✓ Awareness programme should be conducted to the teachers about different dimensions of emotional intelligence.
- ✓ Innovative modern teaching strategies should be incorporated to develop interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence.
- ✓ Training must be given to teachers regarding language laboratory, digital library, e-library and CAI in order to develop verbal linguistic intelligence among the teachers.
- ✓ Teaching strategies should be developed by using different dimensions of intelligence.
- ✓ Workshops and seminars may be conducted for teachers.
- ✓ In-service training must be given to the teachers to develop their multiple intelligence.
- ✓ Democratic approach in administration will enable teachers to be competent in new areas.

Recommendations for the Present Study:

- ✓ Skill based workshops, conferences and seminars must be organized periodically to develop these skills in these areas.
- ✓ Psychological skill based activities to be promoted in teacher education institutions to promote among the teachers.
- ✓ Quality of the programme has to be still more improved to develop the emotional intelligence to teachers.

Conclusion:

Ones intelligence is an innate as well as acquired intellectual potential. Every child is born with some intellectual potential which grows and develops with the help of maturity and experiences. Similarly, one is also born with some innate emotional intelligence in terms of one's level of emotional sensitivity, emotional memory, emotional processing and emotional learning ability. This potential (unlike intelligence) is liable to be developed or damaged as a result of one's experiences. The difference here is between the development pattern of innate emotional intelligence and general intelligence as a result of maturity of experiences.

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